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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“NURTURING YOUNG MINDS: TEACHING THE MATATAG CURRICULUM IN ELEMENTARY CLASSROOMS”

Imparting knowledge among elementary grade pupils is very crucial because these early years nurture not only what children know but also how they see learning that will help in shaping their total personality. The introduction of MATATAG Curriculum has encouraged teachers to go beyond the traditional instruction and embrace a student-centered approach. The curriculum focuses on developing the needed knowledge, values, and skills to become productive, dynamic, and resilient individuals because the teachers' task is to inculcate into their young minds curiosity, analytical and critical thinking, and good character in every child. The MATATAG Curriculum emphasizes mastery of the required skills in literacy, numeracy, and life skills. For elementary pupils, it means creating learning outcomes that are engaging, appropriate, and meaningful. Through this scenario, learners view the relevance of Mathematics in their daily lives and develop problem-solving skills in contexts they understand. Moreover, in other classes, reading activities can be correlated to stories that reflect Filipino values and culture, helping learners connect lessons to their identity and community. Another essential strategy in the MATATAG Curriculum is the development of values formation and the total personality into every learning competency. Elementary learners are naturally curious and inquisitive, they learn not only from what teachers say but also from what teachers ask them to do. That is why teachers need to give emphasis on the importance of respect, kindness, and empathy. Activities that encourage honesty, cooperation, sharing, and helping one another should be a regular part of instruction. Through this, we instill among the learners not only intellectually but also emotionally, morally, and socially.

The use of play and experiential learning activities is another strategy to develop the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains of the learners. Children learn best when they actively engage themselves in collaborative activities like games, role-playing, art activities, and hands-on experiments. This approach makes the classroom into a space of discovery where children can feel excited and enjoy learning. Last is the need for teachers to embrace technology and innovation while maintaining personal and professional commitment. In addition, educational videos, interactive applications, and other related educational technology can make lessons more interesting and appealing to the learners of the present generation. Encouraging questions, giving affirmations, and listening to learners' thoughts are equally important in creating a positive and meaningful learning atmosphere.

Teaching the MATATAG Curriculum for elementary learners is not about inculcating the foundational skills but it is encouraging learners to become strong individuals who are ready to face the challenges of the present educational system. It is about creating classrooms as a place where learning is enjoyable, meaningful, and value-driven. As educators, it is our role to be their mentor, creative facilitators, and

compassionate learning guide. We teach not only knowledge and skills but also shape young hearts and minds to become responsible, confident, and caring members of the entire society.

